

46 - INVESTIGATING E-SPORT: A NEW TREND FOR YOUTH AND ADULTS

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INTRODUCTION

In recent years we have seen a radical change in the way we participate in sports activities and championships. E-Sports is a new world trend that attracts millions of fans around the world and here in Brazil is no different. E-Sports has been unveiled as a new sporting mode with players, loyal fans, fans, strategies and game modes never seen before, which shows a new model of ascent with respect to the taste for the modality.

This paper presents a brief report about the history of this modality, its participants and how it has influenced the media, the game market and the participants themselves. From a bibliographical research we will be able to adapt the knowledge related to E-sports and its nuances. An increasingly real trend in a world where the virtual reaches more and more in our homes, interacting with people in real time. Despite this, the subject is somewhat recent and still needs more studies about it. The content is basically found on the internet. Few books have been written so far.

Unsurprisingly, games attract different audiences and age groups. Since the creation of the first consoles people have sought, for various reasons, to interact more and more in this universe of games. What was just a simple homemade fun where the family participated with friends, began to take on increasing dimensions, in that in these games the interactions happened to be with other people miles away. With the advent of the Internet, it all got easier for and games and applications flood many devices ranging from consoles, smartphones to the simplest cell phones.

If we think about it a little, we can work several goals with games focused on E-Sport since they refer to teamwork, leadership, overcoming obstacles; goals that can help the practitioner in their daily lives. There is no way to halt this worldwide trend, E-sport has come to stay and more and more fans are emerging, generating jobs, millionaire figures and a growing by this activity. A lot can be availed.

In general, e-sports:

"These are games that can be played competitively. They are not limited to sports games such as the FIFA football or Madden series of American football, they cover shooting genres (FPS), strategy (RTS) and battle arenas (MOBA), for example. (PEREIRA, 2014, pág.21).

Even so, there are other discussions about it: whether we are talking about a sport with conventional characteristics. While there is still no consensus, we can see something different. We like to play video games and the possibility of making money from it is something that stimulates anyone who has a certain skill with the controls, a new market that opens up to those who like and want to continue making electronic games to earn a living.

HOW DID E-SPORT COME ABOUT.

The term derives from the English "electronic sports" and is the name intended for the professional competition modes of electronic games (video games), exposes the limits of agility and reasoning ability of the players. Matches are played by teams and in real time. Another definition for e-sports:

"An activity of computer games against other people on the internet, often for money, and often seen by others using an internet, sometimes in special events" (Cambridge Dictionary, 2017).

According to Magalhães (2016) despite not having that name, the first competition happened in 1972 at Stanford University by its students. For this championship was chosen the space battle game "Spacewar". The same author still comments that another landmark for e-sports was the possibility of playing online, live popularizing even more this type of game. During the decades that have passed much has changed. Pereira (2014) mentions that the first games to be competitively contested, through tournaments and championships were the arcades, known in Brazil in the traditional arcades, now installed in entertainment establishments such as malls.

Before that we had only the consoles / video games that brought fun for the whole family. They were played at home and access was very limited, few people could afford it. With the increase in demand and the subsequent fall of values, coupled with the improvement in people's living conditions, access became easier and over time they became popularizing and invading homes around the world.

Over time what was done at home becomes larger as the Internet emerges as a new means of communication, allowing easy access to the information generated. Factors such as the decline of public spaces and the daily commute to work have made people increasingly practice what we call domestic leisure by allowing home-made entertainment. Another advantage of playing this way is that you do not have a specific age group to play (in most games).

Specifically with regard to video games and electronic games, we can say that there may be no physical displacement to play, more and more players will appear and the possibility of challenging them without leaving the comfort of your home is motivating. Thus, games like LOL (League of Legends), FIFA (EA SPORTS) and Starcraft attract millions of fans who spend hours in front of the monitor for competitions. So what was something "homemade" goes through an evolution that has culminated in what we have today.

If we think that electronic games are ever more present in our lives it is not difficult to understand the fascination they arouse in their players. New graphics, better gameplay, multi-platform games and other things glimpse something that goes beyond the simple pleasure of playing. There is an increasing number of practitioners and the gaming industry has also realized this by seeing a huge market thread offering a huge range of games and consumer products. Featherstone (1995) says that One of the premisses of consumer culture is the expansion of capitalist product production.

JUST FUN?

At first, the e-sport world has already consolidated. In Brazil we can say that we are growing a lot. According to

Magalhães (2016) as of 2012, two companies in the market have decided to open offices here. Blizzard Entertainment and Riot Games, developers of the StarCraft2 and League of Legends games respectively. In less than a year they have already held championships betting that here we would have a future in e-sports.

If we take into account that this period of e-sports is on the rise with a large number of fans, attracting more and more sponsors and famous figures, there is something that goes beyond fun. Children and adolescents participating in groups and clans become increasingly involved in this universe that tends to semi-professionalization and why not professionalization.

We know that there are groups that participate in games for fun, to pass the time, competing up, but nothing that refers to values that can be paid. From the moment these values come into play, a lot of change and what was momentary fun, it now shows itself as serious, involving more accurate training, more time in strategizing and a dedication almost exclusively to games. Today e-sport is a phenomenon of acceptance and amplitude among young people mainly.

THE E-SPORT TODAY

There is a lot to be said about electronic games these days. Many themes should be discussed for a breakthrough in relationships among all involved. There are many games and evolution happens exponentially, and e-sport practitioners are eager for news. Thematic fairs are a real success. We can cite as an example the BGS (Brazil Game Show) that gathers the fans for games, electronic games and the like.

With regard to women, for example, GERA (2014) mentions that the pro-game world saw a jump in popularity among women increase between 15 and 30 percent in 2013. The same author also mentions that even with the increase in female audience, the participation of women is almost absent in the arenas. It is well known that the number of men participating in the games is much higher and if we observe specifically among the professionals this becomes even more evident. We should check what happens and provide greater female participation in such events.

The benefits that the practice of electronic games can bring to the practitioner should be studied with greater emphasis since these activities can work the companionship, teamwork, problem solving and overcoming limits, including in school, because "by proposing games where games can be worked concomitantly with various areas of knowledge, it is possible to make the child and adolescent acquire new knowledge" (SANTOS, 2014 p.32).

The preparation that these players have is the subject of discussion. Will it be another market that opens to the professional of Physical Education? Preparing for a tournament or championship requires a lot of participants and proper preparation must be done. We can benefit from this niche market. In addition to the physical preparation we also have the psychological issue of the players that undergo enormous pressure.

The amounts paid today in e-sport go far beyond what we could imagine. The championships pay true fortunes to the participants and some professionals are real celebrities in the middle. Many others also have as their support the electronic game dedicating themselves totally to this modality. The awards to cyber-athletes revolve around the millions of dollars. We are talking here about individual awards and team awards. And more and more amateur players prepare to, perhaps one day, become a true E-sport professional.

Another argument that generates much controversy is to answer the following question: is e-sport a sport? Many players see their work as a sport because they understand that the training, the pressures they undergo and the daily demands would justify the understanding that e-sport should be considered as any traditional sport.

The Michaelis dictionary brings back as a concept of sport:

"Methodical practice of physical exercises aimed at leisure and body conditioning and health. The set of physical activities or games that require skill, which obey specific rules and which are practiced individually or as a team; sport"

Already the Priberan dictionary brings another meaning:

"Regular practice of an activity that requires a corporal exercise and that obeys certain rules, for leisure, for physical development or to demonstrate agility, dexterity or strength ..."

(TUBINO, 1999) mentions that only the modalities that had game, competition, movement were considered sport. This concept prevented several indoor games for a long time from being considered as sports because they did not present movements compatible with the previous requirement of the concept of sport. The same author also states that this changed with the International Charter on Physical Education and Sports of 1979 that made this concept have a relevant social outreach. It is complex to say and there are still no closed arguments on the subject, including with regard to sports legislation.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The e-sports have conquered a legion of fans all over the world and in Brazil it is no different. They also show themselves to be democratic because they can be practiced anywhere. People can set up groups and participate in tournaments in the form of leisure.

There has been a real revolution in the last decades since the emergence of the first games, consoles, computers culminating in the universe we have today. The literature is still small near the range of possibilities that can be addressed in the subject. We see with amazement the speed with which these games evolve and we can say that this trend has come to stay. More and more young people and adults are starting to play this way. A new world that unfolds through the new media. what was simple became something great providing a new form of entertainment, fascinating and embracing more and more and more people.

Players frenetic ones and eyes glued to the computer screen. Playing video games has become a profession and they are idols of e-sport. They have contracts, are sponsored and have fans. It is necessary to study in more depth the subject since there is much to develop on the subject and it is now known that there is a current for electronic games / e-sport to become an Olympic modality, because the games competitions have gained a lot and the talks are already scheduled to become an Olympic modality already at the 2024 Paris Olympics, although there is still a lack of clarity about whether "e-sports really are a sport with regard to physical activity and what is needed to be considered as such, "said IOC President Thomas Bach" (PALAZUELOS, 2017).

As an indication, the proposal to delve into studies related to electronic games also known as e-sport. As it is perceived the pertinent literature still lacks more reliable elements, of a literature that really shows the importance of the subject and can give subsidies for new studies on respect.

Keywords: E-Sport; Tendencies; Youth and Adults

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INVESTIGATING E-SPORT: A NEW TREND FOR YOUTH AND ADULTS

This article presents information about the current trend of electronic games also known as e-sports. E-sports are electronic games that can be played by groups of people in competitions that can offer prizes to the winners. As the days go by more young people and adults practice this new mode of competition that was originally practiced at home with families. With the advent of the Internet and easy access to the games, much has changed, but despite this, the bibliography related to the subject is still scarce and more research is needed on the effects that e-sport has on the participants, the objectives that can be reached with them and the female participation that is still small. Anyway, a lot is still going to happen in this universe called E-sport.

Keywords: E-Sport; Tendencies; Youth and Adults.

INVESTIGATION E-SPORT: UNE NOUVELLE TENDANCE POUR LES JEUNES ET LES ADULTES

Cet article présente des informations sur la tendance actuelle des jeux électroniques également connu sous le nom e-sport. Les e-sports sont des jeux électroniques qui peuvent être joués par des groupes de personnes dans des compétitions qui peuvent offrir des prix aux gagnants. Au fil des jours, de plus en plus de jeunes et d'adultes pratiquent ce nouveau mode de compétition qui était à l'origine pratiqué à la maison avec les familles. Avec l'avènement de l'Internet et un accès facile aux jeux, beaucoup de choses ont changé, mais malgré cela, la bibliographie relative au sujet est encore rare et il faut plus de recherche sur les effets que le e-sport a sur les participants, les objectifs peut être atteint avec eux et la participation féminine qui est encore faible. De toute façon, beaucoup de choses vont encore se passer dans cet univers appelé E-sport.

Mots-clés: E-Sport; Tendances pour les jeunes et les adultes

INVESTIGANDO EL E-SPORT: UNA NUEVA TENDENCIA PARA JÓVENES Y ADULTOS

Este artículo presenta información sobre la tendencia actual de juegos electrónicos también conocidos como e-sports. Los e-sports son juegos electrónicos que pueden ser jugados por grupos de personas en competiciones que pueden ofrecer premios a los ganadores. A medida que los días pasan, más jóvenes y adultos practican esta nueva forma de competencia que originalmente se practicaba en casa con las familias. Con el advenimiento de Internet y el fácil acceso a los juegos, muchas cosas han cambiado, pero a pesar de eso, la literatura relacionada con el tema sigue siendo escasa y es necesaria más investigación sobre los efectos que el deporte electrónico tiene en los participantes, los objetivos que el deporte electrónico tiene en los participantes. Lo que se puede lograr con ellos y la participación femenina sigue siendo pequeña. En suma, mucho aún sucederá en ese universo llamado E-sport.

Palabras clave: E-Sport; Tendencias; Jóvenes y Adultos.

INVESTIGANDO O E-SPORT: UMA NOVA TENDÊNCIA PARA JOVENS E ADULTOS

O presente artigo apresenta informações a respeito da tendência atual dos jogos eletrônicos também conhecidos como e-sports. Os e-sports são jogos eletrônicos que podem ser disputados por grupos de pessoas em competições que podem oferecer premiação aos vencedores. Conforme os dias vão passando mais jovens e adultos praticam essa nova modalidade de competição que era a princípio praticada em casa com as famílias. Com o advento da Internet e o acesso facilitado aos jogos muita coisa mudou, mas apesar disso, a bibliografia relacionada ao assunto ainda é escassa e se faz necessário uma maior investigação sobre os efeitos que o e-sport tem sobre os participantes, os objetivos que podem ser alcançados com eles e a participação feminina que ainda é pequena. Enfim, muita coisa ainda vai acontecer nesse universo chamado E-sport.

Palavras-chave: E-Sport; Tendências; Jovens e Adultos.